

CASMO5 Analysis of HTC Critical Experiments

Joshua Hykes* and Rodolfo Ferrer

Studsvik Scandpower, Inc., 1070 Riverwalk Dr, Idaho Falls, Idaho, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803406

ABSTRACT

The HTC critical experiments, containing fuel with a U-Pu mixed-oxide composition approximating 4.5%-enriched PWR fuel burned to 37.5 MWd/kg, have been analyzed by CASMO5. This includes all four phases of the HTC, which are progressively more complex: (1) fuel moderated and reflected with pure water, (2) fuel with gadolinium or boron poisoned water, (3) absorber canisters similar to a spent fuel pool, and (4) lead or steel screens representing a fuel cask. For Phase 1 and 2, the eigenvalue bias was less than 100 pcm, and the standard deviation was less than 200 pcm, excluding the soluble boron outliers in Phase 2. Excluding the short cores, the CASMO5 eigenvalue predictions for Phase 3 and 4 were mostly within 300 pcm of the experiment. This is a demonstration of CASMO5's accuracy for pseudo-burned fuel, as well as an indication of its robustness over a range of conditions such as pin pitch, assembly gap, and absorber/reflector types.

Keywords: CASMO5, HTC, critical experiments, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

CASMO5 [1] is Studsvik Scandpower's lattice physics code, part of the CMS5 core analysis package. It performs resonance calculations using Equivalence Theory, fine-group collision-probability pin cell calculations, Method of Characteristics 2D neutron and gamma transport, and depletion using CRAM. It has been benchmarked against a range of numerical comparisons (primarily continuous energy Monte Carlo) and experimental measurements, including B&W, DIMPLE, IPEN, TCA criticals, and isotopic comparisons against PIE data, in addition to hundreds of cycles of operating LWR plant measurements when used as part of CMS5. Studsvik continually adds to the set of CMS5 benchmarks, but recently a focused campaign was performed to demonstrate the performance of the codes for high enrichment/high burnup, as part of the supplement to the US NRC relating to these topics [2]. In connection with this effort, recently the HTC experiments [3] were made available to Studsvik by UT-Batelle. The HTC experiments were a set of critical experiments performed in France in the 1980s using mixed U-Pu oxide fuel with water moderator to simulate burned fuel. This is a unique fuel composition, since it allows one to test the code performance for burned fuel, in contrast to most other critical experiments which are limited to fresh fuel only.

The Haut Taux de Combustion (HTC) series of critical experiments [3] were conducted in the 1980s at the Apparatus B facility at Valduc (CEA, France) with the support of IRSN and AREVA. The pin lattices used mixed oxide fuel with water moderation. The ratio of Pu to U was chosen to approximate the ratio in 4.5%-enriched PWR fuel burned to 37.5 MWd/kg. (Although the actinides approximate burned fuel, no fission products are present.) Several configurations of the experiments were performed with multiple variations, covering a range of pin pitches, assembly configurations, soluble poisons, and plate absorbers and shields similar to conditions in a fuel pool or cask. The experiments are documented extensively in Refs. [4-7].

In addition to reporting the experiments in Ref. [3], the authors provided criticality analysis of the experiments using CRISTAL (APOLLO2-MORET 4), TRIPOLI-4.3, and SCALE 5.1. The eigenvalue predictions are mostly within 200-300 pcm, with some larger differences, especially for some of the heterogeneous configurations involving the absorber canisters and cask shields. Ref. 8 provides analysis of the HTC criticals, including eigenvalue predictions, sensitivity/uncertainty analysis, and

* joshua.hykes@studsvik.com

upper subcritical limit (USL) determinations. The report notes a few specific configurations which are outliers in terms of predicted eigenvalues; for example, the eigenvalues for the cases with the cadmium shield are consistently lower than the other absorber plates.

The CASMO5 eigenvalue predictions for Phase 1 and Phase 2 with soluble gadolinium were already reported in Ref. 9, but are repeated here for completeness. The Phase 2 (soluble boron), Phase 3, Phase 4 (lead and steel shields) results are presented here for the first time.

2. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION AND MODELING APPROACH

The HTC criticals were performed in a water tank/pool reactor, meaning that water is the moderator and reflector. The fuel is pellets of mixed oxide U-Pu, with an active height of 90 cm, pellet diameter of 0.794 cm, and outer clad (Zr) diameter of 0.95 cm [3]. The experiments are conducted at temperatures close to 20 degrees C. The technical reports [4-7] provide atom densities for all the compositions. Note that the Pu-241 and Am-241 concentrations are not constant due to decay. Fine reactivity control is achieved via the water height, which ranges from 30-90 cm above the bottom of the active fuel.

The geometric configurations are shown in Figure 1 for Phases 1-4 (based on figures in Ref. [3]). Phases 1 and 2 are representative of fuel in the core (Figure 1a). The Phase 1 and 2 cases use various pin pitches and lattice sizes ranging from 50x50 to 25x24 and 50x17. Phase 1 uses pure water, while Phase 2 has two sets, one with soluble gadolinium and one with soluble boron. The pin pitch ranges from 1.3 to 2.3 cm.

Phase 3 is representative of a spent fuel pool. There are four fuel assemblies, each surrounded by an absorber canister. These canisters are similar to absorber racks, and they are composed of borated steel, boral, or cadmium, each with its own thickness. Several of the cases are conducted with no canister/absorber present. The pin pitch is fixed to 1.6 cm. The distance between the canisters is varied (distance "d" in Figure 1b). The number of pins per assembly is 25x25 or 25x24.

Phase 4 is similar to Phase 3, but it adds lead (10 cm thick) or steel (15 cm thick) screens around the outside of the four assemblies. A water gap is optionally allowed between the canister and screen. This configuration is meant to mimic a fuel cask. All cases use 25x25 pins and 1.6 cm pin pitch.

A number of approximations or simplifications are employed in the CASMO5 models of the HTC. First, the aluminum corner brackets are neglected. Next, symmetry is employed to reduce the geometry size and runtime. The Phase 3 and 4 cases are run with quadrant symmetry. In Phase 3, the canister for the 25x24 assembly is special, such that the absorber plate along the empty pincell row is moved next to the fuel. CASMO5 cannot model this exactly, so the absorber slab is expanded to fill the empty pincell row, decreasing the density to maintain the same number of absorber atoms. The Phase 4 screen geometry is simplified by ignoring the extra portion that extends into the outer reflector.

CASMO5 is a 2D code, and as such requires the axial buckling to account for axial leakage. In this work, the axial buckling is computed by a curve fit to the axial flux computed by a 3D MCNP calculation [9]. Since the calculations are already available, the MCNP results are included alongside the axial buckling and the CASMO5 eigenvalues.

Figure 1 Radial configuration of the HTC experiments, Phases 1 through 4. Figures based on Ref. [3].

3. RESULTS

The Phase 1 eigenvalues are given in Table 1. The average CASMO5 bias is 63 pcm, with a maximum difference of 330 pcm. The one-sigma MCNP statistical uncertainty is listed under the σ_k heading. Tables 2 and 3 provide the results for Phase 2 with soluble gadolinium and boron, respectively. For the soluble gadolinium, the mean bias is -85 pcm, with a maximum difference of -309 pcm. For the soluble boron, cases 1-13 are mostly less than 100 pcm errors, while cases 14-21 have errors significantly higher, up to -785 pcm.

For both Phase 1 and 2, the axial buckling is approximately $10^{-3} / \text{cm}^2$, within the range for which the axial buckling approximation is accurate.

Table 1 Phase 1 eigenvalue results.

Case	Pin Pitch (cm)	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1	
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)	
1	2.3	1.820E-03	0.99960	-40	0.99954	40	-46.3
2	2.3	1.035E-03	0.99889	-111	0.99907	10	-92.9
3	2.3	9.883E-04	0.99890	-110	0.99919	32	-81.4
4	1.9	1.717E-03	1.00174	174	1.00096	48	95.9
5	1.9	1.154E-03	1.00047	47	1.00015	43	15.4
6	1.9	9.875E-04	1.00025	25	0.99958	38	-41.9
7	1.7	1.648E-03	1.00231	231	1.00059	48	59.3
8	1.7	1.347E-03	1.00059	59	1.00061	45	61.4
9	1.7	1.117E-03	1.00157	157	1.00032	45	32.1
10	1.5	1.847E-03	1.00330	330	1.00103	55	102.5
11	1.5	1.260E-03	1.00112	112	0.99951	49	-49.4
12	1.5	1.107E-03	1.00011	11	1.00049	70	49.3
13	1.3	2.084E-03	1.00275	275	1.00098	52	98.1
14	1.3	1.134E-03	1.00037	37	0.99931	47	-69.3
15	1.3	1.012E-03	1.00031	31	0.99870	50	-129.7
16	1.7	1.536E-03	1.00068	68	1.00028	55	28.1
17	1.7	1.120E-03	1.00093	93	1.00024	48	24.2
18	1.7	1.197E-03	0.99738	-262	0.99738	46	-261.8
		Mean	1.00063	62.6	0.99989	45.6	-11.5
		Std. Dev.	0.00144	143.8	0.00094	11.9	94.3

Table 2 Phase 2 with soluble gadolinium absorber in water.

Case	Pin Pitch (cm)	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1	
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)	
1	1.3	1.115E-03	0.99924	-76	0.99930	20	-70
2	1.3	1.003E-03	0.99957	-43	0.99943	13	-57
3	1.3	1.147E-03	0.99865	-135	0.99909	15	-91
4	1.3	1.053E-03	0.99907	-93	0.99921	14	-79
5	1.3	9.686E-04	0.99914	-87	0.99901	14	-99
6	1.3	1.104E-03	0.99803	-197	0.99765	15	-236
7	1.3	9.676E-04	0.99809	-192	0.99806	19	-194
8	1.3	1.028E-03	0.99700	-300	0.99753	14	-247
9	1.3	9.745E-04	0.99691	-309	0.99774	17	-226
10	1.5	9.791E-04	0.99701	-299	0.99759	15	-241
11	1.5	1.045E-03	0.99831	-169	0.99842	14	-158
12	1.5	9.794E-04	0.99817	-183	0.99891	14	-109
13	1.5	1.078E-03	0.99980	-20	0.99903	19	-97
14	1.5	9.751E-04	0.99984	-16	0.99933	17	-67
15	1.5	1.330E-03	1.00181	181	1.00080	17	80
16	1.5	1.082E-03	1.00136	136	1.00054	16	54
17	1.7	1.056E-03	1.00155	155	1.00107	14	107
18	1.9	9.967E-04	1.00067	67	1.00061	17	61
19	1.7	1.061E-03	0.99706	-294	0.99757	17	-243
20	1.7	1.082E-03	1.00165	165	1.00056	16	56
		Mean	0.99915	-85.4	0.99907	15.9	-92.8
		Std. Dev.	0.00163	162.8	0.00117	2.0	117.1

Table 3 Phase 2 with soluble boron absorber in water.

Case	Pin Pitch (cm)	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1	
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	MCNP-6.3 k	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)
1	1.3	1.157E-03	1.00073	73	1.00064	16	64
2	1.3	1.054E-03	0.99959	-41	0.99902	18	-99
3	1.3	1.041E-03	0.99992	-8	0.99933	15	-67
4	1.3	1.023E-03	1.00033	33	0.99998	15	-2
5	1.3	1.041E-03	0.99976	-24	0.99970	14	-30
6	1.3	9.713E-04	0.99983	-17	0.99951	15	-49
7	1.3	9.835E-04	1.00046	46	1.00100	16	100
8	1.3	9.482E-04	0.99949	-51	0.99999	17	-1
9	1.5	9.821E-04	0.99966	-34	0.99989	18	-11
10	1.5	9.749E-04	0.99848	-152	0.99842	18	-158
11	1.5	1.047E-03	1.00043	43	1.00056	14	56
12	1.5	9.929E-04	1.00074	74	1.00055	17	55
13	1.5	1.033E-03	1.00010	10	1.00003	16	2
14	1.5	1.101E-03	1.00412	412	1.00275	18	275
15	1.7	1.078E-03	1.00397	397	1.00368	13	368
16	1.7	1.029E-03	1.00215	215	1.00200	15	200
17	1.7	9.819E-04	1.00335	335	1.00363	12	363
18	1.7	1.001E-03	0.99346	-655	0.99375	14	-625
19	1.7	1.237E-03	1.00136	136	1.00008	12	8
20	1.9	1.008E-03	0.99215	-785	0.99250	16	-750
21	1.9	1.034E-03	0.99667	-333	0.99637	15	-363
Mean			1.00036	36	1.00025	15.6	24.6
Std. Dev.			0.00235	235	0.00220	1.8	220.3

Table 4 shows the Phase 3 eigenvalues. Cases 24 and 25 are excluded due to their short (< 40 cm) partially-flooded cores, which results in an axial asymmetry and larger errors for the axial buckling approximation. The remaining cases are within 500 pcm of unity. As noted in Ref. [8], the reported eigenvalues for the cadmium canister are several hundred pcm lower than the rest.

Table 4 Phase 3 fuel pool configurations with absorber canisters.

Case	Abs. type	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1		
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	MCNP-6.3 k	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)	
1		9.723E-04	0.99972	-28	0.99899	18	-101	
2	Borated steel	2.394E-03	1.00182	182	1.00141	16	141	
3		1.370E-03	0.99802	-198	0.99768	20	-233	
4		9.649E-04	0.99798	-202	0.99708	17	-292	
5		1.881E-03	0.99789	-211	0.99751	19	-249	
6		Boral	9.629E-04	1.00100	100	1.00010	16	10
7		1.106E-03	0.99692	-308	0.99630	12	-370	
8		2.039E-03	1.00289	289	1.00319	17	319	
9	Cadmium	1.492E-03	0.99585	-415	0.99616	11	-384	
10		1.155E-03	0.99657	-343	0.99614	18	-386	
11		1.875E-03	0.99533	-467	0.99564	15	-436	
12		1.066E-03	1.00105	105	0.99973	15	-27	
13		1.000E-03	1.00112	112	0.99981	16	-19	
14		1.142E-03	1.00136	136	1.00046	14	46	
15		1.106E-03	1.00156	156	0.99997	13	-3	
16		1.133E-03	1.00158	158	1.00018	15	18	
17		1.028E-03	1.00164	164	0.99997	17	-4	
18	None	1.120E-03	1.00095	94	0.99986	15	-14	
19		1.215E-03	1.00051	50	0.99895	13	-106	
20		9.661E-04	1.00026	26	0.99906	18	-94	
21		1.277E-03	1.00046	46	0.99993	15	-7	
22		1.105E-03	1.00282	282	1.00200	14	200	
23		1.180E-03	1.00421	421	1.00328	15	328	
26		1.647E-03	1.00151	151	1.00020	19	20	
Mean			1.00013	12.6	0.99932	15.8	-68.4	
Std. Dev.			0.00234	234.4	0.00210	2.3	210.2	

Tables 5 and 6 give the Phase 4 eigenvalues for the lead and steel screens. Lead screen cases 1-3, 17, 27-32, and 35-38 have been excluded due to short critical water heights (< 50 cm). Likewise for steel screen experiments, cases 1-3, 14, and 22-30 are omitted.

Table 5 Phase 4 lead screen eigenvalue results.

Case	Abs. type	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1	
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	MCNP-6.3 k	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)
4		2.139E-03	1.00342	342	1.00026	15	26
5		1.953E-03	1.00280	280	0.99983	16	-17
6		1.635E-03	1.00188	188	1.00004	18	4
7	Borated steel	1.485E-03	1.00206	206	1.00011	15	11
8		1.893E-03	1.00187	187	0.99908	14	-92
9		1.826E-03	1.00133	133	0.99848	14	-152
10		1.779E-03	1.00056	56	0.99829	17	-171
11		1.743E-03	0.99986	-14	0.99808	15	-192
12		1.309E-03	1.00272	272	1.00150	17	150
13		1.326E-03	1.00216	216	1.00094	13	94
14	Boral	1.267E-03	1.00126	126	1.00026	16	26
15		1.019E-03	0.99812	-188	0.99690	16	-310
16		1.217E-03	0.99804	-196	0.99723	16	-277
18		2.044E-03	1.00162	161	0.99910	16	-90
19		1.562E-03	1.00127	127	0.99912	15	-88
20		1.372E-03	1.00124	124	0.99998	16	-2
21	Cadmium	1.500E-03	0.99926	-74	0.99805	16	-195
22		1.411E-03	0.99864	-136	0.99713	14	-287
23		1.346E-03	0.99794	-206	0.99683	14	-317
24		1.297E-03	0.99735	-265	0.99661	19	-339
25		1.207E-03	1.00071	71	0.99955	13	-45
26		1.063E-03	1.00092	91	0.99968	17	-32
33	None	1.905E-03	1.00782	782	1.00270	14	270
34		1.701E-03	1.00663	663	1.00252	15	252
		Mean	1.00123	122.9	0.99926	15.5	-73.9
		Std. Dev.	0.00250	249.9	0.00170	1.5	169.8

Table 6 Phase 4 steel screen eigenvalue results.

Case	Abs. type	Buckling (/cm ²)	CASMO5 k - 1		MCNP-6.3	MCNP-6.3 k - 1	
			CASMO5 k	(pcm)	MCNP-6.3 k	σ_k (pcm)	(pcm)
4		2.177E-03	1.00507	507	0.99819	15	-181
5		2.019E-03	1.00369	369	0.99832	16	-168
6		1.963E-03	1.00185	185	0.99734	14	-266
7	Borated steel	1.877E-03	1.00116	116	0.99708	13	-292
8		1.818E-03	1.00021	21	0.99687	15	-313
9		1.778E-03	0.99928	-72	0.99634	16	-366
10		1.696E-03	1.00305	305	0.99817	18	-183
11		1.549E-03	1.00322	322	0.99872	15	-128
12	Boral	1.380E-03	1.00421	421	1.00096	16	96
13		1.278E-03	0.99987	-13	0.99640	14	-360
15		2.145E-03	1.00279	279	0.99733	14	-267
16		1.696E-03	1.00188	188	0.99751	15	-249
17		1.611E-03	0.99933	-67	0.99531	15	-469
18	Cadmium	1.499E-03	0.99833	-167	0.99516	19	-484
19		1.422E-03	0.99724	-276	0.99478	17	-522
20		1.351E-03	0.99682	-318	0.99485	15	-515
21		1.484E-03	1.00277	277	0.99785	15	-215
31		2.145E-03	1.00667	667	1.00012	14	12
32	None	1.777E-03	1.00568	568	1.00011	14	11
33		1.532E-03	1.00546	546	1.00004	16	4
		Mean	1.00193	192.8	0.99757	15.3	-242.7
		Std. Dev.	0.00285	284.9	0.00182	1.5	182.2

The CASMO5 eigenvalues from all phases are plotted in Figure 2 as a function of axial buckling. The figure shows that most cases are within 400 pcm of unity, with a few outliers with up to 800 pcm error. The Phase 4 cases have a positive trend with respect to axial buckling and the Phase 1 results have a slight positive trend, while Phase 3 does not show such a trend. (The range of buckling for Phase 2 is small, so it is difficult to make a conclusion of the trend in this case.)

Beyond the trend with respect to axial buckling, the bias and uncertainties of the four phases are roughly similar; that is, their scatterplots mostly overlap. This demonstrates robust predictive power for CASMO5 over a range of absorbers (soluble and discrete) and reflector/shielding materials. The mean CASMO5 eigenvalue over all cases listed in the tables above (127 cases in total) is 1.00049, with a standard deviation of 248 pcm.

Figure 2 CASMO5 eigenvalue versus axial buckling.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The HTC critical experiments Phases 1 through 4 have been analyzed with CASMO5. Excluding the outlier cases 14-21 from the Phase 2 soluble boron, the mean eigenvalue bias for Phases 1 and 2 was less than 100 pcm with a standard deviation less than 200 pcm. This demonstrates excellent code accuracy for LWR fuel with a range of pin pitches and array sizes, and in the presence of soluble gadolinium and boron.

The Phase 3 results with absorber canisters were mostly within 200 pcm. The exceptions were the cadmium sheets, which were too low by 300-500 pcm, and cases 24 and 25, which were very short cores.

Many of the Phase 4 cases with lead and steel screens used short critical water heights, and the accuracy is compromised for those cases. For the taller cores, CASMO5's accuracy is similar to Phases 1-3, even though Phase 4 has significant heterogeneity. The mean eigenvalue bias was between 100 and 200 pcm, with the standard deviation between 250-300 pcm.

Overall, the HTC criticals are well documented and able to be predicted accurately by a number of tools, including CASMO5. This analysis is a further demonstration of CASMO5's accuracy, particularly for burned fuel. The CASMO5 results are robust over a range of conditions and parameters, including variations in pin pitch, assembly gaps, absorbers, and reflectors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. gained access to the HTC experimental data (Refs. [3-7]) through an agreement with UT-Batelle. James Carnal created the CASMO5 models of HTC for Phases 1 and 2 [8].

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Rhodes, K. Smith, and D. Lee, "CASMO5 Development and Applications," *Proc. PHYSOR 2006*, Vancouver, B.C., September 10–14, (2006).
- [2] Generic Application of the Studsvik Scandpower Core Management System to Pressurized Water Reactors: Supplement for Extended Enrichment, Burnup, and SMRs, SSP-14-P01/028-TR-S1, Studsvik Scandpower (2025).
- [3] Fernex, F., Ivanova, T., Bernard, F., Létang, E., Fouillaud, P., & Thro, J. F. (2009). HTC Experimental Program: Validation and Calculational Analysis. *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **162**(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE07-52>
- [4] F. Fernex, HTC Programme: Mixed Plutonium (1.1 Wt%) Uranium (1.57 Wt.-%-Enriched) Dioxide Rods, Part 1: Water-Moderated and Reflected Simple Arrays, DSU/SEC/T/2005-33/D.R., Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (2008).
- [5] F. Fernex, HTC Programme: Mixed Plutonium (1.1 Wt%) Uranium (1.57 Wt.-%-Enriched) Dioxide Rods, Part 2: Reflected Simple Arrays Moderated by Poisoned Water with Gadolinium or Boron, DSU/SEC/T/2005-38/D.R., Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (2008).
- [6] F. Fernex, HTC Programme: Mixed Plutonium (1.1 Wt%) Uranium (1.57 Wt.-%-Enriched) Dioxide Rods, Part 3: Pool Storage, DSU/SEC/T/2005-37/D.R., Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (2008).
- [7] F. Fernex, HTC Programme: Mixed Plutonium (1.1 Wt%) Uranium (1.57 Wt.-%-Enriched) Dioxide Rods, Part 4: Shipping Cask, DSU/SEC/T/2005-36/D.R., Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (2008).
- [8] D.E. Mueller, K.R. Elam, and P.B. Fox, "Evaluation of the French Haut Taux de Combustion (HTC) Critical Experiment Data," NUREG/CR-6979, ORNL/TM-2007/083, 2008. <https://info.ornl.gov/sites/publications/Files/Pub6615.pdf>
- [9] J. Carnal, J. Hykes, and R. Ferrer, "CASMO5 Analysis of Select HTC Critical Experiments Simulating Burned Fuel," In IHLRWM-2025, Washington, DC, (2025). ans.org/pubs/proceedings/article-59678/